

Relevance of Teaching of Isms in the B.Ed Curriculum

Key words :

Naturalism, Idealism, Pragmatism, Realism.

The study of isms (mainly naturalism, idealism, pragmatism and realism) gives a sense of 'meaning' to the educational practitioner for his work and its place in the general scheme of life. It enables him to see clearly the relationship between his day-to-day, so called the routine work and the goals of an individual, social and national life. He will not feel that he is lost in the wilderness counting the trees without having an idea of the horizons. It would help him to adjust himself to his work to fit in a square peg and if necessary to try to change in his own possible ways the status quo. This paper tells how teaching of isms gives a purpose and a direction to life which he would be able to infuse in children or teachers as the case may be.

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Today's life is extremely busy, with its hectic pace, relations getting stressed, too much violence, and corruption and so on and so forth. The present generation of youth who are pursuing their studies does not seem to have the time for anything at all. In the little time they manage to spare themselves, they often tend to fall prey to various distractions that life presents before them. The youth is the wealth of the nation. Shaping them properly and helping them develop their personalities will let their hearts flower, making them better citizens of the world, who would go ahead and create a better tomorrow. The present generation of youth is currently experiencing a lot of stress, worries and tensions. They tend to age faster and fall prey to various illnesses and ailments.

To overcome from this condition youth need some guide lines which are provided by the teacher who influenced by isms i.e. idealism, naturalism, pragmatism, realism etc. The teachings mentioned in the idealism and naturalism can be used to help them view their own lives from a different perspective, enriching them spiritually, letting them lead a quality life. . Idealistic philosophy believes that this planned creation has two parts-(1) The teacher and (2) The child as student only one target is aim of both. – The individual child development in a spiritual way. This aim is realized only through education and by the essential agent i.e. the teacher. An Idealist teacher's personality is full with self-knowledge, self-dynamism and essential qualities which are essential for spiritualism. He tries to shape the individuality of the child to a life of purity, virtue and great achievements by presenting himself as a role model. He should create an atmosphere by his own activities and planned experiences for the child, which is suitable for child. He also gives the instructions to the child with genuine love, affection and sympathy that he attains his full mental and spiritual development. For idealists spiritual

world is more important than the material world. According to Horne- "Idealism holds that the order of the world is due to the manifestation in space and time of an eternal and spiritual reality." Idealism emphasizes on the values namely, Truth, Beauty and Goodness. These values will develop the development of a moral character of a child, which aim is self – realization of all individuals by one's own efforts. Therefore, it promotes universal education. Idealism gives the importance to the individuality of a child and tries to stimulate his creative energies. Idealism follows the principle of self-discipline, which help an individual to develop of the 'Self' of an individual.

In the present world of today which is full of stresses, strains, conflicts, envies and material struggles, the need of idealistic education is greatly essential for peaceful living of human beings devoted to social good and national welfare. Naturalism is child-centred focus on study of child, called child psychology. Naturalism believes that the laws of nature govern life and social goals are less important than individual goals. Natural setting like lakes, mountains, and other outdoor conditions provide number of opportunities where naturalists make learning laboratories by using natural settings, by which individuals work on their skills while enjoying leisure time. By the philosophy of naturalism teachers of physical education fully satisfied. Truth and things valued exist within the physical realm of nature. "Everything according to nature" means students learn and develop new skills in and through nature. If an individual is physically fit, it enhances a readiness to learn mental, moral, and social skills. Individualized learning occurs through self-discovery and exploration of one's capabilities and interests. Through problem-solving, students develop skills at their own rates. Naturalism has the potential to revolutionize our relationship to ourselves, to others, to society and to the planet. A deep appreciation of nature,

naturalism shows our full connection to the nature, it leads to an ethics of compassion, and it gives potential to us for greater control over our circumstances. Thus, naturalism should help to realize our inherent unity with the nature.

James describes 'Pragmatism', "The pragmatism method is primarily a method of solving metaphysical disputes which are unending." Pragmatism is a method which emphasizes on the result, it doesn't follow any predetermined truth means it didn't accept any true which one proved in earlier. It only accept as true which have some utility for human beings and follow the changes according to time. Pragmatism emphasizes on the practical aspect of life. According to the pragmatism, to develop such powers in a child that makes able to understand his environment and try to construct new facts or ideals. By it, he develops social and democratic skills. We should use education to develop above qualities in the child by which he will understand his environment and adjust with this environment. Without determined principles it is very difficult task to construct curriculum, that's why to attain aims of pragmatism curriculum should be keep on changing. Curriculum should follow the principle of utility, principle of interest, principle of activity, principle of activity, principle of experience and principle of integration. To follow this principles pragmatism uses Dewey experiment method which is called problem-solving method and Kilpatric's project method. In these methods needs, interest, aptitudes and abilities keeps in mind, in which opportunities are given to the children to solve the problems in real life situations. So, pragmatism gives the opportunities and abilities to solve the real life situations.

Realism is the western philosophy which considers matter as real and true. They believe that universe is made from matter and matter has its own independent existence. But some realists disbelieve in the existence of the world itself. All realists have different views on the soul

and God. Most of realists accept the existence of God, heaven and hell but it is based on religion and belief so it is not definite because knowledge about matter is theoretical. Berkeley who may be taken to the represent the position proclaimed the now famous "To be is to be perceived". Education for the realists is to make life happy, physical development and senses training, to develop mental faculties, give knowledge of natural and social environment, develop scientific attitudes, to develop vocational education. All subjects should be included in the curriculum which are essential or related with the life of human beings. They focus on vocational education. Dr. Broudy who presents the realist view point in education defines the common aim of education as a preparation for the "Good life". As Broudy defines in the context of the school: "The task of the school is to transcribe the good life, the good individual and the good society into learning that presumably will contribute to the production." A healthy good life is followed by four principles i.e. principles of self-preservation, self-determination, self-realization and self-integration. Self-preservation is an appetitive principle and is the physiological base of a healthy personality. 'Self-determination' helps a person to see the reality and understand his strengths and limitations. Realism philosophy is based on practical approach. Its emphasis on the reality-orientation would help an individual to preserve his mental health. In a vast expanding scientific and technological universe where knowledge increases exponentially, a philosophy that justifies the acquisition of knowledge is worth its place.

Conclusion :

Teaching of isms in B.Ed. is necessary for B.Ed. students who are going to be secondary teachers in future. Teacher education programmers are meant for professional preparation of teachers and so they should provide for a comprehensive coverage of professional knowledge, values and

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